

(Semi-structured) Interview protocol - Using GenAI tools to support inception-stage software startups

Part I: Background questions

- Do you have any working experience in software development?
For example: Product Manager, Software Engineer, UI/UX Designer, Project Manager
- Can you briefly describe the responsibilities in your current/previous role?
- What technologies and tools are you familiar with to support your current/previous role?

- What do you understand by Generative AI (GenAI)?
- What GenAI technologies and tools are you familiar with?
- What is your opinion on GenAI tools in general?

- What is your experience with startups or entrepreneurial activities?
- How long have you been involved in startups or entrepreneurial activities?
- Could you describe your role or position within the startup ecosystem?

Part 2: Usage of GenAI in inception-stage startup process

In the ideation and problem identification phase, did you use any GenAI tools to brainstorm on what startup idea you could work on? If yes:

- What are these tools?
- How did you use them?
- What is your opinion on them? (How useful are they?bad question, leading)

In the problem validation phase, did you use any GenAI tools to validate the problem? If yes:

- What are these tools?
- How did you use them?
- What is your opinion on them? (How useful are they?bad question, leading)

In the validation of the problem-solution fit phase, did you use any GenAI tools to build the MVP, set up analytics, etc.? If yes:

- What are these tools?
- How did you use them?
- What is your opinion on them? (How useful are they?bad question, leading)

Part 3: Other questions

- What GenAI tools have you used to brainstorm, create pitch videos, and pitch slide decks?
- Are there any other GenAI tools you have used? For what purpose?
- What is your opinion on the future of applying GenAI technology to support startups?